

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CENTER POINT OF INDONESIA (CPI) AREA IN ECONOMIC GROWTH AND THE EASTERN INDONESIA REGION

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Abstract

The development of the Center Point of Indonesia area is a large infrastructure project that aims to increase economic growth and community welfare in Eastern Indonesia. Like many other large-scale projects, the development of Center Point of Indonesia has the potential to cause significant impacts on the environment, including changes in air, water, and soil quality, as well as reduced biodiversity. Given the importance of maintaining a balance between development and environmental sustainability, this research is urgently needed. This research is important to understand and manage the environmental impacts of the Center Point development in Indonesia. These impacts, if not handled properly, can cause irreparable ecological damage, disrupt local ecosystems, and affect the welfare of local communities. Comprehensive data and analysis will help stakeholders make better decisions regarding the development of future infrastructure projects. This study aims to assess the impact of the development of the CPI Area on environmental quality (air, water, soil, and biodiversity). Analyze the socio-economic changes in the surrounding community as a result of this development.

Keywords: Regional Development; Center Point of Indonesia; Environmental Impact; Sustainability; Impact Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Large-scale infrastructure development such as the Center Point of Indonesia Area often has significant impacts on the surrounding environment (Dwiatmoko et al, 2020). These impacts can be in the form of changes in air, water, and soil quality, as well as reduced biodiversity. Often, these impacts are not fully taken into account in the project planning stage, so mitigation efforts made are not optimal (Juharni et al, 2024). Given the importance of maintaining a balance between development and environmental sustainability, this research is very urgent to be carried out.

Indonesia is actively developing infrastructure to support economic growth and improve people's welfare (Salim et al, 2024). The Center Point of Indonesia Area Project is one of the ambitious projects that is expected to become a new economic center in Eastern Indonesia. This project involves the construction of large commercial, office, residential, and recreational facilities (Thamrin Abduh, 2018). While the economic benefits are clear, the environmental impacts of a project of this magnitude need to be understood and managed properly to prevent irreparable damage (Wulandari et al, 2020).

Makassar City as the capital city of South Sulawesi Province continues to grow in boosting development progress along with civilization that also continues to advance. In 2021, the 4.3 km AP Pettarani elevated toll road was inaugurated in Makassar to support transportation accessibility (Karim et al, 2023). Accessibility is the ease and speed of reaching and connecting one location to another. Of course, it must be with an adequate transportation network.

In addition, accessibility is also a means to realize good connectivity between regions (Handayani et al, 2022). We know in economics, the smoother a transportation system is to support the connectivity of a region, indicates the economic health of the region in question (Lipseý & Sjöholm, 2011). Likewise, the slower the transportation and connectivity, the more sluggish the economy in the region (Karim et al, 2023).

In addition to the AP Pettarani toll road, Makassar also has another city icon, namely the Center Point of Indonesia. CPI is intended as an integrated global business center. Built on a 157-hectare reclamation area facing directly onto the open sea of the Makassar Strait. In its aim to strengthen the Center Point of Indonesia as an integrated business area, a modern mega project has also been built which is designated as a business area.

Although this area is still under construction, the Center Point of Indonesia has become a magnet for Makassar residents to carry out various activities such as exercising, recreating, and taking pictures in various corners of the iconic Center Point of Indonesia. In addition to being a central business area, on the other hand, the Center Point of Indonesia also plays a role as a decent public space because this area is very easily accessible to Makassar City residents. As a central business area, the Center Point of Indonesia area will certainly absorb a lot of labor.

This is because the construction of various facilities and infrastructure such as offices, hotels, malls, restaurants, campuses, housing, tourism, and other sectors such as the goods industry will be carried out. That way, the real sector will automatically grow and the financial turnover in Makassar City will increase (Karim et al, 2021). South Sulawesi Province with Makassar as its capital city has long been known as the gateway to Eastern Indonesia.

Given the strategic position of Makassar City, it is also supported by various adequate facilities and infrastructure such as flyovers, ports, and international-class airports (Mardjuni et al, 2022). So, it is not surprising that Makassar has experienced such rapid progress in various sectors which of course have an impact on economic growth (Karim et al, 2022). Moreover, with the presence of the Center Point of Indonesia which is intended as an integrated business center, it will make Makassar City even more advanced as a gateway to Eastern Indonesia. This means that with all these advantages, it will certainly have a positive impact on regional progress.

Previous research has shown that large infrastructure projects can cause serious environmental degradation, including decreased water and air quality, loss of natural habitats, and disruption to local flora and fauna (Fitriyah, 2024). For example, the construction of similar projects in Jakarta and Surabaya has caused increased air and water pollution, as well as decreased biodiversity around the project area. Learning from these cases, it is very important to conduct a comprehensive environmental impact analysis and implement effective mitigation measures at every stage of development (Daga et al, 2024).

In addition to environmental impacts, large infrastructure development can also have socio-economic impacts, both positive and negative, on the surrounding community (Abduh et al, 2023). While some communities may benefit economically through job creation and improved access to amenities, others may face forced displacement, loss of traditional livelihoods, and

rapid social change (Hossain, 2006). Therefore, this study will also evaluate the socio-economic impacts of the project to provide a more complete picture of the consequences of development (Anas et al, 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Economic Interaction of Development Center Point of Indonesia

The development of Center Point of Indonesia on the coast of Makassar City is one example of the reverse impact in Myrdal's theory. This area was originally a livelihood location for fishermen, which was then reclaimed and continued with the development of Center Point of Indonesia (Aginta, 2021). The concept of Center Point of Indonesia itself is a modern city area, Citra Land City Losari Makassar, which is integrated with housing and commercial centers.

Center Point of Indonesia will be built on an area of 157 ha, around 50 hectares of reclaimed land was handed over to the South Sulawesi Government. The land will be a public area for the construction of public facilities, such as mosques, state guesthouses, parks, and others (Hill, 2018). The rest of the land is given to the private sector to manage the area to develop a new city called Citra Land City Losari for housing and commercial areas.

We can see that the division of the land will benefit the private sector because the government only gets 32% even though the land belongs to the state. The existence of Center Point of Indonesia as a form of a waterfront city is a form of realization of the vision of Makassar City for 2014-2019, namely making Makassar City a world city. Several forms of development are encouraged to achieve this. The essence of development is for the common good and welfare.

The development of the Center Point of Indonesia Makassar mega project has an impact on the marine ecosystem, damaging fishery resources which results in marine sedimentation and marine pollution. Automatically, it will be more difficult for fishermen to find fish (Hasniati et al, 2023). The development of the Center Point of Indonesia project has also changed the quality of sea water which used to be clean and clear, now polluted by waste from the development of the Center Point of Indonesia.

The economic downturn which is the impact of the presence of the CPI Makassar shows how the Cost Benefit Analysis concept is not used as a tool in formulating the impact of the development of the CPI Makassar. Shellfish seekers are also affected by the damage to the marine ecosystem due to this reclamation development (Mardjuni & Karim, 2024), it used to be easy for shellfish seekers to get shellfish, in two to three hours they could collect a full sack, now there is only one place to find shellfish and even fewer (Suharyadi et al, 2009). There used to be six types of shellfish, but now there are only three, one of which is green shellfish which is not very popular because there was news that green shellfish in Losari were polluted and poisonous.

This reclamation project also eliminates water absorption areas because it is the main road across the Tanjung Bunga metro, which is the access to the reclamation project, so during the rainy season, flooding often occurs.

The construction of this road also eliminates coral reefs and mangrove areas, whose main function is to absorb carbon released from industrial areas, especially in urban areas such as Makassar City, which ultimately causes the loss of biodiversity in Makassar waters, which will contribute to increasing the effects of global warming (Syahrudin & Karim, 2020). In addition, the impact of this reclamation project also leaves the area where the fish auction is located on Jalan Rajawali as a puddle and a place for sedimentation to accumulate. The pier that used to be lined with fishing boats from morning to evening is no longer visible. And now its condition is like a small pool with pitch-black water (Oktavia et al, 2023).

2. Cost Benenfit Analysis

Cost-benefit analysis is a calculation process to determine the impacts caused by economic activities and so on. In the context of the development of the Center Point of Indonesia, conflict analysis is an approach used to measure the social problems of the development of the Center Point of Indonesia in Makassar City, namely seeing a society consisting of various groups competing to control strategic resources, such as power, finance, and authority to impose a value on society (Abduh et al, 2024). The resulting policy direction recommendations are focused on the target group of beneficiaries, namely the affected community including fishermen, porters, fish farmers, epe banana traders, MSMEs, and housewives who are also affected by the development of the Center Point of Indonesia.

Development is a process of change to improve human living standards that cannot be separated from the activity of utilizing natural resources. In these activities, changes often occur to the ecosystem and natural resources (Sobirin et al, 2023). The changes made will certainly have an impact on the environment. In urban areas, the most obvious environmental problems are problems caused by land use. There are three main causes, including;

- (1) Factors of increasing population growth both naturally (births) and migration from villages to cities (urbanization),
- (2) Development factors that always dominate urban areas, and
- (3) Factors of limited urban land.

Land use problems in Makassar City are also beginning to be felt, this is due to the increasing population growth every year which is accompanied by the development of business activities in it (Verico. 2023). As we know, the impact of increasing population density will affect community welfare and sustainable social impacts. Coastal reclamation is one example of human efforts to overcome land limitations in urban areas, such as what happened in Makassar City, the reclamation activity carried out was the Development of the Center Point of Indonesia in the Losari Beach Area. Makassar City Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2015 concerning the Makassar City Spatial Planning Plan for 2015-2034, the Center Point of Indonesia area is designated as an Integrated Global Business Center. The development of Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) was built in an area with a total area of 600 hectares, consisting of business and government centers, holiday areas, and world-class hotels equipped with golf courses with views of the open sea and views of the islands in Makassar Bay. In further development, the

area was used for the development of urban and residential facilities (Wahin & Ikhsan, 2019). The coastal reclamation process has not been going well in reality, so it is feared that it will have negative impacts such as the increasing amount of material being washed away, resulting in shallowing of the waters, and if this continues it will threaten the coastal ecosystem. Another thing that happens due to the presence of CPI in Makassar City also hurts marine sustainability. This reclamation project also eliminates water catchment areas because it is the main road crossing the Tanjung Bunga metro line which is access to the reclamation project, so that flooding often occurs during the rainy season (Solihin et al, 2021).

The construction of this road also eliminates coral reefs and mangrove areas whose main function is to absorb carbon released from industrial areas, especially in urban areas such as Makassar City, which ultimately causes the loss of biodiversity in Makassar waters, thereby increasing the impact of global warming (Nurlaili & Cahyadin, 2019). In addition, the impact of this reclamation project also made the fish auction area on Jalan Rajawali become a puddle and a place where sedimentation accumulates. The pier that used to be crowded with fishing boats from morning to evening is now no longer visible. And now its condition is like a small pool with pitch-black water.

METHOD

This study aims to determine the impacts that occurred after the development of the Center Point of Indonesia Area on the environment using Qualitative Descriptive Analysis and SWOT Analysis. The variables used consist of abrasion, sedimentation, and water quality. Data was obtained from several informants ranging from the Regional Government, both the Executive and Legislative Institutions, Community Leaders, Fishermen Leaders, and Youth Leaders. From the Analysis Results used, one of them produced that abrasion, sedimentation, and water quality have an impact on existing environmental conditions ranging from the plains to the waters around the Center Point Indonesia Area.

The instruments for collecting data in this study are

- (1) Identification and in-depth understanding of the impact of the development of the Center Point of Indonesia area on the environment;
- (2) Simulation models that can predict the impact of development with high accuracy;
- (3) Policy recommendations and mitigation solutions to reduce negative impacts (Sugiyono, 2011).

This research method will allow us to better understand the impact of the development of the Center Point of Indonesia area on the environment and to develop solutions that can reduce its negative impacts. With collaboration between various experts and stakeholders, it is hoped that this research can provide a positive contribution to sustainable development.

Research flow diagram

Figure 1: Research framework

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Objective description of research location

Makassar City is the fourth largest city in Indonesia and the largest in Eastern Indonesia with an area of 175.79 KM² with a population of 1,112,688, making this city a metropolitan city. As a service center in KTI, Makassar City acts as a center for trade and services, a center for industrial activities, a center for government activities, a hub for goods and passenger transportation services by land, sea, and air, and a center for education and health services. Astronomically, it is located at 119°24'17"38" East Longitude and 5°08'6"19" South Latitude. Makassar City is located on the West Coast of Sulawesi Island. Based on its geographical location, Makassar City has the following administrative boundaries:

- (1) To the north it borders Maros Regency and the Makassar Strait;
- (2) To the south it borders Gowa Regency and Takalar Regency;
- (3) To the west it borders the Makassar Strait; and (4) To the east it borders Maros Regency and Gowa Regency.

Table 1: Area of Makassar City

No	Sub-district	Area (km ²)	Percentage
1	Mariso	1.82	1.04
2	Mamajang	2.25	1.28
3	Tamalate	20.21	11.50
4	Rappocini	9.23	5.25
5	Makassar	2.52	1.43
6	Ujung Pandang	2.63	1.50
7	Wajo	1.99	1.13
8	Bontoala	2.10	1.19
9	Ujung Tanah	4.40	2.50
10	Kepulauan Sangkarrang	1.54	0.88
11	Tallo	5.83	3.32
12	Panakkukang	17.05	9.70
13	Manggala	14.14	13.73
14	Biringkanaya	48.22	27.43
15	Tamalanrea	32.84	18.11
	Makassar City	175.77	100.00

Source: Author's findings, 2024.

The population of Makassar City based on the results of the 2020 population census was 1,423,877 people. Compared to the results of the 2010 population census, the population of Makassar City experienced a growth of 0.60 percent. Meanwhile, the large sex ratio in 2020 of male to female population was 99.19. The population density in Makassar City in 2020 reached 228,231 people/km². The population density in 15 Sub-districts is quite diverse with the highest population density in Makassar Sub-district with a density of 32,566 people/km² and the lowest in the Tamalanrea Sub-district at 3,240 people/km². For more details, see the following table.

Table 2: Population density by Sub-district

Sub-district	Population (thousands)	Population density per KM ²
Mariso	57,426	31,552.75
Mamajang	56,049	24,910.67
Tamalate	180,824	8,947.25
Rappocini	144,587	15,664.90
Makassar	82,067	32,556.27
Ujung Pandang	24,526	9,325.48
Wajo	29,972	15,061.27
Bontoala	54,996	26,188.57
Ujung Tanah	35,789	8,133.66
Kepulauan Sangkarrang	14,125	9,172.08
Tallo	144,977	24,867.41
Panakkukang	139,590	8,187.10
Manggala	146,724	6,078.04
Biringkanaya	209,048	4,335.30
Tamalanrea	103,77	3,240.48
Total	1,423,877	228,231.46

Source: Author's findings, 2024.

2. Analysis of the impact of the development of Center Point of Indonesia

Historically, the development of the Center Point of Indonesia megaproject began at the end of 2013, marked by the reclamation of reclamation activities on the Losari coast. As an initial stage, landfilling was carried out around the Tanjung Delta Maccini Sombala area, Tamalate Sub-district. In 2015, the reclamation or sea-filling activities carried out by the developer were stopped by the RTRW Special Committee and the Makassar City Government. This suspension was temporary, waiting for certainty regarding the allocation of reclamation space which would be discussed by the Makassar City RTRW Draft Regional Regulation Special Committee 2015-2035. This development continued in 2016 when Boskalis was the winner of the reclamation tender and was expected to be completed in March 2018.

In addition, the development of the CPI continued until 2017 when the Main Bridge was completed. Then at the end of 2017, the 99 Kuba Mosque and the State Guest House were completed. Along the way, the development of the Center Point of Indonesia area certainly has an impact that will affect the surrounding coastal environment. The following are the impacts caused by the development of the Center Point of Indonesia Area.

2.1. Abrasion

Abrasion is a process of releasing the return energy of ocean waves towards the land, crashing into the coastal area, then washing away "land debris" along the coastal slope and finally deposited in the sea. The greater the wave strength, the greater the abrasion, the more "land debris" is washed away. Based on data from the South Sulawesi Provincial Disaster Management Agency, the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) area is an area that is in danger of abrasion with low to high levels. In this condition, attention needs to be paid so that in the future it can produce solutions or strategies that will become a reference for the government and developers to develop the Center Point of Indonesia area into an Integrated Global Business Strategic Area in Makassar City. which can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Abrasion hazard index in the Center Point of Indonesia area

No	Indeks Bahaya	Luas (Ha)
1	Rendah	4,21
2	Sedang	1,61
3	Tinggi	15,13
	Luas Bahaya Abrasi	20,94
	Luas Wilayah Kawasan CPI	119,05
	Persentase Bahaya Abrasi	17,58%
Source: Author's findings, 2024.		

Based on the results of the table above, it can be concluded that the area included in the abrasion hazard zone is 20.94 Ha or around 17.58% of the area of the Center Point of Indonesia area.

Figure 3: Map of Center Point of Indonesia

Source: Source: Author's findings, 2024.

2.2. Sedimentation

Sedimentation is the process of deposition of eroded material in a certain place. Deposition of material can be caused by water, wind, ice, or glaciers in a basin which then forms a new type of rock called sedimentary rock. The deposits that collect into new rocks consist of abiotic components, such as soil and sand that come from weathering or erosion over a long period (Tirtosuharto, 2022). Sedimentation that occurs in the Center Point of Indonesia area, is caused by Coastal Reclamation and the presence of deposits originating from the development of new land in the coastal reclamation area. In addition, it is influenced by the speed of the tidal current and ebb current which we can see in the picture below:

Figure 4: Tidal current speed around CPI

Source: Source: Author's findings, 2024.

We can see in the image above that the condition of the waters towards high tide, the movement of the current pattern around the CPI waters shows the general direction of the current moving from the sea entering towards the coast. Around the sampling point, the current turns from east to west at a speed of 0.32 - 0.40 m / s.

Figure 5: Water Conditions

Source: Source: Author's findings, 2024.

We can see in the image above that the water conditions are receding. In receding water conditions, the movement of current patterns around the CPI waters shows that the current generally moves from the east towards the sea at a speed of 0.22 - 0.24 m / s. It can be concluded that the curve in the CPI area causes sand deposits originating from the west, resulting in sedimentation in the area. The main impact is the obstruction of shipping routes due to the shallowing of the sea, the death of marine organisms, and decreased biodiversity, thus hampering the livelihoods of the local community (Kusumatrisna et al, 2022).

The construction of the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) which carried out reclamation of 157 Ha has had an impact on changes in fishing areas and sea lanes for fishing communities in Panambungan Village. Before the reclamation of the Center Point of Indonesia was carried out, fishermen's sea lanes to fishing areas did not take too long, only about 30 minutes. After the reclamation was carried out, fishermen's sea lanes had to pass through the reclamation area which took approximately 20 minutes with a narrow river path and across a bridge connecting the CPI area with Losari Beach. Thus, the community's fishing areas also changed by heading further towards the Makassar Strait. Then for boat access routes, according to respondents, the construction of the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) has disrupted the access route for fishing boats to enter and exit. Previously, the route for fishermen to go out to catch fish from the Rajawali fish auction site was not that far, now fishermen have to make a detour to go in and

out to catch fish, so this also results in increasing operational costs by increasing the fuel needs of fishermen and then there is shallowing and narrowing of the route due to the reclamation of the Center Point of Indonesia area.

DISCUSSION

The development of the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) can have a positive impact on economic growth in Makassar and South Sulawesi. This development is also expected to reduce the gap between the Western Region of Indonesia and the Eastern Region of Indonesia whereas in the second quarter of 2021, the contribution of National GDP was still dominated by Java Island at 57.92% and Sumatra Island at 21.73% (BPS, 2021). This economic growth can be realized, among others, with various economic potentials that will be generated. The development of the business and entertainment sector, presence of the Center Point of Indonesia project was built with various facilities, where the largest percentage is a business center covering an area of 32.9 ha (21%) and various entertainment centers. The existence of this new business center and entertainment center will certainly increase the circulation of money which will provide a large multiplier effect on the wheels of the economy. The business fields that will be most affected are estimated to be the tertiary sector, including wholesale and retail trade, transportation and warehousing, provision of accommodation and food and beverages, information and communication, financial services and insurance, real estate, and corporate services. The presence of several facilities from the development of the Makassar City CPI provides development to the business and entertainment sectors (Ruslan et al, 2023). The socio-economic impact of coastal reclamation is the accommodation of residents' needs for a place for interaction and socialization as well as a place to trade or sell, thus providing job opportunities for residents (Bahtiar et al, 2021). Increased local revenue of the Regency and City in the Mamminasata Metropolitan area and South Sulawesi Province. This is due to the existence of new sources of taxes and levies from various economic activities in the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) and its surrounding areas. This increase in local revenue will then increase the regional fiscal capacity index so that the region will be more independent in carrying out its development. The reduction in the proportion of the national revenue and expenditure budget in development in the Makassar area and its surroundings will have a broad impact because the national revenue and expenditure budget can be used more in other areas to realize equitable development. Tax sources presented through economic activities after the presence of the economy have an impact on increasing local revenue (Abduh & Remmang, 2023).

Employment can increase during development or after development is completed. During development, the workforce needed is construction workers. Construction workers who do not require special skills should be taken from residents whose businesses are disrupted by development (fishermen, shrimp farmers, laborers. After development is complete, the workforce needed will be more diverse, especially related to the trade and service sectors (Karim & Syamsuddin, 2024). Affected communities who are employed as construction workers during the construction of the Center Point of Indonesia must still be accommodated after the Center Point of Indonesia is operational. In addition to construction training, other

training is also needed that is by the needs of the developing economic sector in the Center Point of Indonesia. The presence of coastal development in this case CPI will create jobs for the surrounding community in the form of trade and services (Karim et al, 2023). Public services that need to be developed to support the Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) from an economic perspective include 1) Availability of space that can be utilized for economic activities, especially to build a global business strategy area; 2) Provision of infrastructure for business actors for product marketing; and 3) Ease of business permits for investors. These public services are formulated to optimize the positive impacts that will be generated from the development of CPI. These public services, in addition to supporting investors, also need to support local community development (Wahyuni et al, 2022). Business actors need to be directed to involve the surrounding community in running their businesses.

As for the prospects for public services expected by the affected community after the construction of the Makassar City CPI, it can be seen in the research of Faisal and Khairil (2019) entitled "The Cross-Cross of Sustainable Urban Development in the Capital Vortex (Case Study: Makassar CPI Reclamation Mega Project) explaining that the community also wants to be employed there, according to the promises of the developer and the government. So that they get decent jobs. And as for the victims of eviction due to the construction of the reclamation project, they want to be given decent housing, not just abandoned.

CONCLUSION

Reclamation and development of Center Point Of Indonesia is a major project that has a significant impact on various aspects of people's lives. This paper aims to explain the possible impacts of the reclamation and development of Center Point Of Indonesia, both positive and negative impacts. The development of Center Point of Indonesia (CPI) in Makassar City is a major project that has the potential to have a significant impact on water quality in the area. This paper aims to explain the impact of declining water quality due to the development of CPI, including the factors that influence it and mitigation efforts that can be made. The development of CPI involves a land reclamation process around the coastal area of Makassar City. This process can cause damage to natural habitats, including the destruction of marine and estuary ecosystems.

The impact of coral reef destruction, loss of mangroves, and sedimentation can directly affect water quality around the CPI development project. One significant negative impact is increased sedimentation. Construction activities and changes in land use can cause increased sedimentation in the waters around CPI. The accumulation of this sediment can reduce water transparency, inhibit the growth of marine organisms, and hurt the life of aquatic biota. One indicator to measure the current state of water quality around the Center Point Indonesia area is to study the population of Macrozoobenthos in the waters of Makassar City. Macrozoobenthos are vertebrate species that are visible to the naked eye without the aid of tools and live around rocks at the bottom of the water. This Macrozoobenthos cannot move quickly and its large size makes Macrozoobenthos very easy to recognize, and is in the waters and at the bottom of the water. The water quality around the Center Point of Indonesia area is

also affected by the operation of hospitals, shopping centers, and several hotels in the surrounding area which are then channeled through several channels, one of which is the Jongaya Canal, so that water pollution increases. The impact of water pollution also damages the local ecosystem. Changes in water quality can affect living organisms, including fish, aquatic plants, and microorganisms. If water quality continues to decline, this can result in the death of aquatic biota and disrupt the food chain. Erosion and sedimentation can also occur, destroying habitats and reducing biodiversity around CPI. Water pollution in CPI can also have long-term impacts on the welfare of the surrounding community. For example, farmers who rely on water from polluted natural sources will face problems in irrigation and agriculture.

In addition, water quality problems can also impact the tourism sector, reducing people's interest in visiting and spending time in the area. In conclusion, the development of CPI in Makassar City has the potential for a significant decline in water quality. This decline in water quality can occur through waste pollution and damage to aquatic ecosystems due to the reclamation process. In handling it, comprehensive mitigation efforts are needed, including strict environmental supervision, good waste management, and involving active participation from the community. Only then can the development of CPI be carried out without sacrificing water quality and environmental sustainability in Makassar City.

References

- 1) Abduh, T., & Remmang, H. (2023). The Effects of Market Orientation and Innovation on Marketing Performance: A Survey of 5 SMEs in the Creative Industry Sector in Makassar City. *Journal of Public Administration and Government*, 5(2), 274-279.
- 2) Abduh, T., Remmang, H., Abubakar, H., & Karim, A. (2024). Entrepreneurship and MSME market orientation toward creative industries: Society Era 5.0 in Makassar city. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 14(2), 76-87. <https://doi.org/10.55493/5002.v14i2.4964>
- 3) Abduh, T., Remmang, H., Palisuri, P., & Karim, A. (2023). Leadership Model and Work Motivation of Employees Research and Development Planning Agency for Regional South Sulawesi Province. *target*, 95 (146.22), 154.
- 4) Aginta, H. (2021). Spatial dynamics of consumer price in Indonesia: convergence clubs and conditioning factors. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Regional Science*, 5(2), 427-451. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41685-020-00178-0>
- 5) Aginta, H., & Someya, M. (2022). Regional economic structure and heterogeneous effects of monetary policy: evidence from Indonesian provinces. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 11(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40008-021-00260-6>
- 6) Anas, T., Hill, H., Narjoko, D., & Putra, C. T. (2022). The Indonesian economy in turbulent times. *Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies*, 58(3), 241-271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00074918.2022.2133344>
- 7) Bahtiar, A. S., & Karim, A. (2021). The Role of BUMDes in Sustainable Economic Development at Enrekang Regency. *Journal of Logistics, Informatics and Service Science*, 1, 117-132. DOI:10.33168/LISS.2021.0108
- 8) Daga, R., Karim, A., Nawir, F., Lutfi, A., & Jumady, E. (2024). Analysis of Social Media Marketing Technology and Online-Based Consumer Purchase Interest in South Sulawesi. *Quality–Access to Success*, 25(199), 330-337. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/25.199.36>

- 9) Dwiatmoko, H., Supriyatno, D., & Mudjanarko, S. W. (2020). The role of railway infrastructure development on the regional economic growth. *International Journal of Sustainable Construction Engineering and Technology*, 11(1), 125-135. <https://doi.org/10.30880/ijscet.2020.11.01.013>
- 10) Fitriyah, A. T. (2024). The Influence Of Modern Agricultural Technology On The Productivity Of Local Food Crops. *International Journal Of Social And Education*, 1(3), 621-631.
- 11) Handayani, B. D., Yanto, H., Pujiati, A., Ridzuan, A. R., Keshminder, J. S., & Shaari, M. S. (2022). The implication of energy consumption, corruption, and foreign investment for sustainability of income distribution in Indonesia. *Sustainability*, 14(23), 15915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315915>
- 12) Hasniati, H., Indriasari, D. P., Sirajuddin, A., & Karim, A. (2023). The Decision of Women in Makassar City to Entrepreneur. *Binus Business Review*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.21512/bbr.v14i1.8936>
- 13) Hill, H. (2018). Asia's third giant: A survey of the Indonesian economy. *Economic Record*, 94(307), 469-499. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-4932.12439>
- 14) Hossain, A. A. (2006). Sources of economic growth in Indonesia, 1966-2003. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 6(2).
- 15) Juharni, J., Sobirin, S., Dewiana, D., & Karim, A. (2024). The Implementation of Community Policing Policies in the Era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 to Prevent Social Conflict in the Maros Resort Police Area. <https://doi.org/10.59670/ml.v21i2.5853>
- 16) Karim, A., & Syamsuddin, I. (2024). Realization of Village Funds in Regional Economic Growth at Enrekang Regency. *The Seybold Report*. 19 (3), 820 – 834. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10934652
- 17) Karim, A., Asrianto, A., Ruslan, M., & Said, M. (2023). Gojek Accelerate Economic Recovery Through the Digitalization of MSMEs in Makassar. *The Winners*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.21512/tw.v24i1.9388>
- 18) Karim, A., Musa, C. I., Sahabuddin, R., & Azis, M. (2021). The Increase of Rural Economy at Baraka Sub-District through Village Funds. *The Winners*, 22(1), 89-95. <https://doi.org/10.21512/tw.v22i1.7013>
- 19) Karim, A., Ruslan, M., Burhanuddin, A., Taibe, P., & Sobirin, S. (2023). Contribution of Village Funds to Regional Economic Recovery in South Sulawesi Province. *SEIKO: Journal of Management & Business*, 6(1), 573-589.
- 20) Karim, A., Syamsuddin, I., & Asrianto, A. (2023). Profitability Ratio Analysis Profit Growth Pt. Gudang Garam Tbk On The Idx For The 2014-2021 Period. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 7(2), 649-660. DOI : 10.29040/ijebar.v7i2.9133
- 21) Karim, A., Syamsuddin, I., Jumarding, A., & Amrullah, A. (2022). The Effect of Gender Independence and Leadership Style on Audit Quality in Makassar Public Accounting Offices. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 5(7), 114-126. <https://doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v5i7.341>
- 22) Kusumatriana, A. L., Sugema, I., & Pasaribu, S. H. (2022). Threshold effect in the relationship between inflation rate and economic growth in Indonesia. *Bulletin of Monetary Economics and Banking*, 25(1), 117-132. <https://doi.org/10.21098/bemp.v25i1.1045>
- 23) Lipsey, R. E., & Sjöholm, F. (2011). Foreign direct investment and growth in East Asia: Lessons for Indonesia. *Bulletin of Indonesian economic studies*, 47(1), 35-63. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00074918.2011.556055>
- 24) Mardjuni, S., & Karim, A. (2024). Improving The Performance Of State Civil Apparatus Through Work Effectiveness At Makassar Regional Human Resources Development Center. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(4), 2831-2840. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i4.1690>

- 25) Mardjuni, S., Thanwain, I. N., Abubakar, H., Menne, F., & Karim, A. (2022). Business Sustainability In Food And Beverage Processing Industry Through Innovation In Maros Regency, Indonesia. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 57(6). <https://doi.org/10.35741/issn.0258-2724.57.6.85>
- 26) Nurlaili, R. U., & Cahyadin, M. M. (2019). Economic and non-economic factors effect per capita income in Indonesia. *Economics development analysis journal*, 8(4), 315-323. <https://doi.org/10.15294/edaj.v8i4.31105>
- 27) Oktavia, W., Abriana, A., & Fitriyah, A. T. (2023). Karakteristik Sensoris Cokelat Pasta Hasil Conching Dengan Metode Couverture. *PALLANGGA: Journal of Agriculture Science and Research*, 1(1), 01-08.
- 28) Ruslan, M., Karim, A., & Haris, A. (2023). Model for Strengthening Micro-, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Supporting Sustainable Economic Enterprises. *Nongye Jixie Xuebao/Transactions of the Chinese Society of Agricultural Machinery*, 54(10).
- 29) Salim, A., Mustafa, M., & Karim, A. (2024). Integrating Environmental Resilience-Based Spatial Utilization for Eco-Industrial Park: Sustainable Industrial Development. *Migration Letters*, 21(1), 371-391. <https://doi.org/10.59670/ml.v21i1.5186>
- 30) Sobirin, S., Taking, M. I., Burchanuddin, A., Karim, A., & Mandala, S. (2023). Potential Analysis of the Agricultural Sector in the Development of an Agropolitan Area in Maros Regency. *Nongye Jixie Xuebao/Transactions of the Chinese Society of Agricultural Machinery*, 54(8).
- 31) Solihin, A., Wardana, W. W., Fiddin, E., & Sukartini, N. M. (2021). Do government policies drive economic growth convergence? Evidence from East Java, Indonesia. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9(1), 1992875. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2021.1992875>
- 32) Sugiyono, P. (2011). Metodologi penelitian kuantitatif kualitatif dan R&D. *Alfabeta, Bandung*.
- 33) Suryahadi, A., Suryadarma, D., & Sumarto, S. (2009). The effects of location and sectoral components of economic growth on poverty: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of development economics*, 89(1), 109-117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2008.08.003>
- 34) Syahrudin, A. K. (2020). The Role of Cooperatives in Economic Growth in Makassar City During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Ijisrt. Com*, 5(10).
- 35) Thamrin Abduh, S. E. (2018). *Strategi Internasionalisasi UMKM* (Vol. 1). SAH MEDIA.
- 36) Tirtosuharto, D. (2022). The impact of fiscal efficiency on poverty reduction in Indonesia: Institutional factor and geographical differences. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, 24(1), 67-93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10109-021-00359-1>
- 37) Verico, K. (2023). *Indonesia's International Economic Strategies*. Springer Nature.
- 38) Wahid, A. N., & Ikhsan, M. (2019). Policy reforms in Indonesia: a political economy perspective. In *The ASEAN Region in Transition* (pp. 25-41). Routledge.
- 39) Wahyudin, W., Tan, S., Junaidi, J., Zulgani, Z., & Zevaya, F. (2024). Dynamic model in analyzing Indonesia's agricultural sector's macroeconomic performance. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(8), 5661. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i8.5661>
- 40) Wahyuni, N., Kalsum, U., Asmara, Y., & Karim, A. (2022). Activity-Based Costing Method as an Effort to Increase Profitability of PT. Anugrah Ocean Wakatamba. *Jurnal ASET (Akuntansi Riset)*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.17509/jaset.v14i2.45642>
- 41) Wulandari, D., Narmaditya, B. S., Prayitno, P. H., Ishak, S., Sahid, S., & Qodri, L. A. (2020). Nexus between production input and price commodity: An integration analysis of rice barns in East Java of Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(10), 451-459. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no10.451>